

MAXILLARY COMPLETE DENTURE REINFORCED WITH TITANIUM MESH: A CASE REPORT

Surabhi Pravin Dudhe¹, Prajakta Thool², Ankita Agrawal,³VijayBhavrao Desai⁴

¹Medical officer, Indira Gandhi Government Medical College and Hospital, Mominpura,Nagpur India.

² Reader, Swargiya Dadasaheb Kalmegh Smruti Dental College and Hospital, Hingna, Nagpur India.

³PG Student, Department of Prosthodontics, Bhabha College of Dental Sciences, Bhopal, India

⁴Vijay Bhavrao Desai, Assistant Professor, Ajman University, UAE

Corresponding Author – Dr Surabhi Pravin Dudhe
Medical officer,Indira Gandhi Government
Medical College and Hospital, Mominpura,Nagpur India.

ABSTRACT

Complete dentures are a complex prosthetic treatment which requires an understanding of prosthetic rehabilitation on a comprehensive level. The repeated fracture of the prosthesis is one of the main challenges encountered when providing single complete denture treatment. The problem can be addressed by incorporating metal mesh into denture bases. Metal mesh reinforcement in denture provides satisfactory and economic solution for such cases. This clinical report presents a case of successful rehabilitation of an edentulous maxillary ridge using denture metal mesh incorporated into the heat-cure acrylic denture base material.

Keywords: Single complete denture, Titanium mesh, heat cure acrylic denture, rehabilitation.

I INTRODUCTION

Prosthodontists are challenged by the conventional acrylic resin denture fracture. When single maxillary dentures are placed adjacent to natural mandibular teeth, the incidence of midline fractures increases. Denture fractures are caused by flexural fatigue, cyclic deformation, and factors altering the stress distribution on the base. The advancement of materials and techniques is essential to avoiding such fractures. There are several ways of increasing denture fracture resistance and decreasing chances of failure, including the use of metal reinforced denture bases, acrylic resin bases reinforced with wire nets, carbon fiber, PMMA reinforced with glass fibre,^{6,7} Lucitone 199, Trevalon high, Paladon ultra and visible light polymerized resin⁸.

II CASE REPORT

A 72-year-old male patient visited our dental office with the primary complaint of difficulty in chewing due to lost upper and lower teeth. The patient had been on medicine for hypertension since 5 years. He denied having any additional systemic disorders. Extra-oral examination

indicated bilateral facial symmetry, with no TMJ clicking or popping sounds heard. An intraoral examination revealed fully edentulous upper and lower arches. According to the house categorization, the patient's ridge form is class I. Patient was explained about different treatment options like full mouth implant supported with prosthesis, Dual arch implant supported overdenture, cast metal maxillary denture and mandibular removable partial denture, Reinforced with titanium mesh maxillary denture and mandibular removable partial denture. Patient declined implants and a cast metal maxillary denture for economical concerns. The patient chose a titanium mesh reinforced maxillary denture and a removable partial denture for the mandible. This cost-effective solution improved denture strength and fracture resistance. Patient's written consent was taken before starting with the procedure.

III PROCEDURE

1. Primary impression of maxillary and mandibular edentulous arches was made with impression compound (Rolex) Fig 3.
2. Maxillary and Mandibular special tray was fabricated using auto polymerizing acrylic resin Fig 4.
3. On the second visit, border molding was done using the custom tray with low fusing impression compound (DPI pinnacle, India) and a final wash impression was made using zinc oxide eugenol impression paste (DPI impression paste) Fig 5.
4. Master cast was poured with dental stone. Maxillary and mandibular permanent record bases and occlusal rims were made on respective master casts and tried in patient's mouth.
5. Using Facebow, the orientation relation was recorded Fig 8.
6. Transferring the Facebow record to the Hanau Wide-View Articulator Fig 9.
7. After recording centric relation, maxillary and mandibular cast was mounted on articulator Fig.10.
8. Teeth arrangement was done in class I relationship Fig 11.
9. The patient underwent a try-in procedure to ensure that the trial denture fit, functioned, and looked well.

Following the standard protocol, the mandibular and maxillary temporary denture with the tooth arrangement was invested and dewaxed. The maxillary record base was covered with a titanium mesh prior to packing, and the denture was packed using heat-cure denture base material and cured according to protocol. Following bench cooling, the denture was removed, finished and polished. Patient was taught about insertion and removal of denture intraorally and post insertion all instructions were given. Patient was recalled for follow up appointment.

IV DISCUSSION

The challenges associated with providing comfort, function, good aesthetics, and retention for the maxillary complete denture patient with natural opposing teeth might be difficult. The patient

must be carefully prepared. It gives the new complete denture patient time to adjust to the denture and allows the dentist to assess his patient physically and mentally before fabricating the final complete denture. Despite the availability of improved implant-supported treatment methods, heat-cure based single maxillary full dentures reinforced with titanium mesh are still the first choice for many restorative dentists when treating such problems.

This study describes a technique for developing and constructing a maxillary single complete denture with titanium mesh that oppose the lower edentulous arch. The usage of denture mesh gives substantial advantages, especially focusing on reducing the wearing away of acrylic tissue.

V CONCLUSION

Rehabilitation of Single Completely edentulous arch has always posed a challenge to the Clinician. For Patients who frequently suffer from denture fractures and heavy occlusal loads, Dentures reinforced with metal mesh provides advantages of strength, fracture resistance and retention over conventional complete dentures.

REFERENCES

1. Ellinger CW, Rayson JH, Henderson D. Single complete denture. *J Prosthet Dent.* 1971; 26(1):4-10.
2. Zarb GA, Bolender CL, Hickey JC, Carlsson GE.
3. Boucher's prosthetic treatment for edentulous patients. 11th ed St. Louis: CV Mosby, 1990:503.
4. Carl F. Driscoll, Radi M. Masri. Single maxillary complete denture. *Dent Clin N Am* 2004; 48:567- 583.
5. Mattie and Rodney D. Phoenix. A precise design and fabrication method for metal base maxillary complete dentures. *J Prosthet Dent* 1996; 76:496-9.
6. Bhandari S. Outcome of single maxillary complete dentures opposing mandibular teeth: A need to introspect on the prosthodontic treatment protocol. *J Indian Prosthodont Soc* 2016; 16:15-9.
7. Kore A, Vaswani P, Khandagle T, Jadhav S. Masking Complete Denture Reinforcements Of Metal Mesh- A Technical Report. *Int J Current Res* 2015;7(10): 21820-21823.
8. Bruce RW. Complete Dentures Opposing Natural Teeth. *J Prosthet Dent.* 1971 ;26(5):448– 55.

Fig 1- Intraoral Completely Edentulous Maxillary Ridge

Fig 2 - Completely Edentulous Mandibular Ridge

Fig 3- Maxillary and Mandibular primary impression with impression compound

Fig 4- Maxillary and Mandibular Special tray with cast

Fig 5- Border molding followed by secondary wash impression with zinc oxide eugenol impression paste

Fig 6 - Fabrication of Permanent Record Base by Incorporation of titanium Mesh

Fig 7 – Jaw Relation done in patients mouth

Fig 8 - Facebow transfer

Fig 9 – Transfer of Facebow to Hanau Articulator

Fig 10 – Mounted Cast on Hanau Articulator

Fig 11-Teeth arrangement done

Fig 12-Mesh incorporated in maxillary single denture

Fig 13.Denture Insertion in Patients Mouth